

Using single-particle ICP-MS for unravelling the effect of type of food on the physicochemical properties and gastrointestinal stability of ZnONPs released from packaging materials.

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the application of Single-Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS) to study the effect of different types of food (orange juice and chicken breast) on the fate of zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs) migrated from two widely employed food packaging materials (polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and low density polyethylene (LDPE)). The gastrointestinal stability of ZnONPs was also evaluated. The idea behind this study is to track for first time the transformations underwent of nanoparticles in the different steps of their route from packaging to the consumer. The presence of high amount of dissolved zinc in the samples notably influenced size detection limit and the accuracy of SP-ICP-MS measurements. The diameter limits of detection (LODd) were 26 nm, 95 nm, 108 nm and 129 nm for aqueous solution, chicken breast extract and for oral and intestinal extracts, respectively. ZnONPs characterization in juice was not possible with SP-ICP-MS due to nanoparticles size was below LODd. Besides difficulties, SP-ICP-MS after extraction with Tris-HCl allowed us to determine that a 72% of the ZnONPs that migrated to chicken breast were smaller than 95 nm. Complementary to SP-ICP-MS, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) enabled to detect small nanoparticles (<3 nm). The combination of TEM and SP-ICP-MS measurements indicated that nanoparticles in chicken reach the intestine wall as small particles (< 10 nm), as aggregates (> 200 nm) and as ionic zinc whereas in case of juice only small nanoparticles (<3 nm) and ionic zinc were detected in the intestinal step.

Keywords: ZnO nanoparticles; Single-Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS); orange juice; chicken breast; *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion.

1. Introduction.

The use of nanomaterials in the food sector has exponentially grown in recent years. Nanomaterials have been employed with several purposes such as food additives, nutrient delivery systems, for the encapsulation of bioactive food components, and for developing nanosensors to detect contaminants. However, nanomaterials have been mostly applied to develop new food packaging materials with the aim of increasing the self-life of the product [1-3]. Although the existing benefits of incorporating nanoparticles in packaging has been extensively reported, the risks associated from the exposure to the nanomaterials are a matter of concern. As a consequence, several studies have appeared in the literature that evaluates nanoparticles migration from the packaging materials into food in order to perform safety assessments [4-6]. The reported studies are mostly focused on quantifying the percentage of nanomaterials released from the food packaging into food simulants following the European Union regulation N° 10/2011 for plastic materials and articles intended to be in contact with food [7]. Unfortunately, most studies do not consider the transformation of nanoparticles (morphology, size and aggregation state) once they interact with the food contained in the package. Food samples are heterogeneous matrices in terms of composition, structure and properties and, consequently food matrix may alter the original properties of nanoparticles. These transformation processes may impact on the potential toxic effects of nanoparticles [8]. For example, Grombe *et al.* 2013 found that tomato soup matrix produced a decrease in the size of SiO₂NPs from 60 nm to 30 nm as well as favouring nanoparticles agglomeration, although individual NPs were still detected [9]. Peters *et al.* 2014 and Loeschner *et al.* 2013 also reported a decrease of AgNPs size along with a 60% reduction in particle mass concentration when they were added to chicken meat samples [10-11].

Based on the previously mentioned, the role of food matrix on nanoparticle stability is a key parameter to accurately evaluate the impact of nanoparticles exposure through the diet and from food packaging materials. In order to achieve this goal, reliable analytical techniques are required to face the important task of characterizing, detecting and quantifying nanoparticles in complex matrices. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has recently launched a document addressing the main guidelines to perform risk assessment of nanomaterials intended to be used in the food and feed area. The Appendix C of this guidance includes a list of suitable analytical techniques to be used for this purpose and also emphasizes the need to apply several techniques (being mandatory the application of transmission electron microscopy (TEM)) [12]. Lately, Single-Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS) has emerged as a reliable technique to determine the analytical parameters required by the EFSA guidance such as particle size and size distribution, particle concentration in terms of mass (g kg^{-1}) and particle number (particles L^{-1}), and the mass fraction of nanoparticle presents as ionic form [12-14].

According to the EFSA guidance, it is also crucial to evaluate the gastrointestinal fate of nanoparticles. Once nanoparticles are ingested they pass through different zones of the gastrointestinal tract where their composition, size and aggregation state may be altered. In this sense, McClements *et al.* 2017 indicated that the effect of type of food is usually not considered in these studies although the effect of food matrix on the properties of gastrointestinal fluids can lead to changes in the fate of nanoparticles after oral ingestion [15].

Hence, the main goal of this study is to examine and to get a better understanding of the role of food matrix on the physicochemical properties and gastrointestinal stability of nanoparticles released from food packaging materials. For this study ZnO nanoparticles

were selected because of their antimicrobial and UV light blocking properties, without impairing polymer transparency. All these characteristics made them suitable for being included into packaging materials [16-19]. Consequently, ZnONPs were incorporated into two widely employed food packaging films, polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and low density polyethylene (LDPE). The ZnONPs-containing plastic films were brought into contact with two food matrices, orange juice and chicken breast, under different contact times. TEM and SP-ICP-MS were the analytical techniques selected in the current study to determine particle size and size distribution, nanoparticle concentration and the dissolved metal fraction of ZnONPs migrated from packaging to food. Moreover, an *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion procedure was carried out after performing migration test in order to evaluate the characteristics of nanoparticles reaching the intestine wall. The idea behind this study is to track for first time the transformations underwent of nanoparticles in the different steps of their route from packaging to the consumer. Moreover, the limitations of SP-ICP-MS when applied to highly soluble nanoparticles as ZnONPs are also highlighted.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Synthesis and characterization of ZnO nanoparticles (ZnONPs)

ZnONPs were synthesized by means of a sol-gel method and by employing gelatine as stabilizer. The synthesis was carried out following the procedure described by Darroudi *et al* 2014 [20]. In brief, 4.5 g of $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were dissolved in 10 mL of Milli-Q water and then stirred for 30 min. Meanwhile, 0.2 g of gelatine were dissolved in 40 mL of Milli-Q water and stirred for 10 min at 40°C until a clear gelatine solution was obtained. Afterwards, zinc nitrate solution was added dropwise to a solution of gelatine and the resulting mixture was subsequently stirred during 12h in a silicone bath at a fixed

temperature of 60°C. The resulting product was submitted to calcination at 600°C during 5 hours to obtain ZnONPs.

ZnONPs were fully characterized in terms of size, morphology, composition and concentration by employing multiple techniques such as TEM (JEOL JEM 2100; USA) equipped with an Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDXS) microanalysis composition system (Oxford Inca), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), UV-VIS Spectroscopy and SP-ICP-MS. Moreover, zeta potential and Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) measurements were performed using a Malver Zetasizer Nano ZS (Malver Instrument LTD, Malvern UK) system equipped with a laser of 633 nm.

2.2 Preparation of food packaging films containing ZnONPs

Two polymeric films widely employed for food packaging (polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and low density polyethylene (LDPE)) were loaded with ZnONPs by following a simple procedure based on a physical interaction between particles and the surface of the plastic films. First, films were cut into small pieces of 2.5 cm x 1.2 cm and then 0.5 mL of ZnONPs aqueous dispersion were added to the surface of plastic films. After that, films loaded with ZnONPs were placed inside an oven at 60°C overnight. Once the deposition of ZnONPs was completed, plastic films with ZnONPs were vigorously shaken using a mechanical shaker in order to remove those nanoparticles that were not adhered to the surface. The final amount of ZnONPs in PET and LDPE films was 0.01 mg mm⁻² and 0.007 mg mm⁻², respectively.

PET and LDPE loaded with ZnONPs were finally characterized by SEM (JEOL JSM 6335). Samples were mounted on SEM stubs with carbon tape and were gold sputter-coated at 2.0 mA for 1 min. The images were taken at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV.

The total zinc content in PET and LDPE films before and after being loaded with ZnONPs was measured by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (FAAS; Perkin Elmer 1100, Waltham, MA) following microwave acid digestion with HNO₃/H₂O₂. The experimental conditions for FAAS measurements are listed in Table 1.

2.3. ZnONPs migration from plastic films to food

Migration studies were carried out by using food matrices instead of food simulants as several studies have reported the important effect of food matrix on physicochemical properties of nanoparticles. The food matrices selected for the current study were orange juice and chicken breast. Both food matrices were acquired in a local market.

Concerning to experiments about migration in orange juice, rectangular pieces of PET doped with ZnONPs were immersed into a glass vial containing 5 mL of orange juice. The glass vials were sterilized and closed to reproduce as much as possible the storage conditions taking place in juice packages. Samples were left to stand for 1, 7 and 15 days at 4°C. Three replicates were carried out for each selected condition. Once the incubation period was completed, plastic films were removed and total zinc concentration was determined in both orange juice and plastic films matrices. Zn concentration was measured by FASS after acid digestion with HNO₃/H₂O₂ 3:1 in a microwave oven. Furthermore, changes on nanoparticles size and morphology were evaluated by TEM and SP-ICP-MS measurements by taking an aliquot of each condition for each period of time. Related to migration studies employing chicken breast, 1g of chicken breast was cut into small pieces and packaged with the LDPE film loaded with ZnONPs. Samples were left to stand during 1, 14 and 26 days at 4°C. Once the selected time of storage was completed, the release of ZnONPs to chicken matrix was monitored by measuring total zinc content in chicken and LDPE film by FAAS. As it was described above, changes on nanoparticles size and morphology were determined by TEM and SP-ICP-MS. However, in this case,

a previous extraction step was required to isolate nanoparticles from chicken breast matrix. For this purpose, two extracting procedures were tested: 1) aqueous extraction with Tris-HCl at neutral pH and 2) enzymatic extraction with protease and Tris-HCl at neutral pH. For this purpose, 5 mL of the corresponding extractant medium were added to the chicken breast samples followed by applying probe sonication during 2 min at 40% of microwave amplitude.

2.4 *In Vitro* gastrointestinal digestion assays

The *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion procedure was carried out by simulating the digestion conditions that occur in the mouth, stomach and intestine according to the procedure described by Böhmert *et al.* 2013 [21]. For this purpose, PET and LDPE films loaded with ZnONPs were put in contact with orange juice and chicken breast and were left to stand during the periods of time already described in the section 2.3. After that, PET and LDPE films were removed and food samples were subjected to an *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion procedure. In the oral step, 5 mL of synthetic saliva was added. The mixture was then stirred at 200 rpm and 37°C during 15 min. Afterwards, the gastric digestion step began by adding 12 mL of freshly prepared gastric solution acidified with HCl to get a final pH value of 1.8 and then the resulting mixture was shaken at 200 rpm and 37°C for 2 h. Subsequently, the pH was adjusted to 6.8 with saturated sodium bicarbonate to stop the gastric process. Finally, for the intestinal digestion step, 17 mL of intestinal solution were added. The mixture was shaken at 200 rpm and incubated at 37°C for 2h. 2 mL-aliquot from each step was removed for its further characterization by TEM and SP-ICP-MS. Moreover, another 2 mL-aliquot was taken from each step in order to determine the amount of Zn in the soluble fraction by FAAS. The composition of synthetic juices employed is detailed in Table 2.

The ubiquitous nature of Zn can lead to problems with contamination from reagents. Moreover, Zn is naturally present in food of different type. To avoid errors and overestimation of Zn contents, blank samples were analyzed in parallel. Chicken breast and orange juice samples packed with PET and LDPE in absence of ZnONPs were considered as blanks samples and they were employed in each of the experiment performed (migration studies and *in vitro* gastrointestinal assays). The reported concentrations of Zn from samples (chicken and orange juice in contact with ZnONPs-containing PET and LDPE films, and gastrointestinal extracts) were calculated by subtracting the amount of Zn from blanks samples

2.5 Single-Particle Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (SP-ICP-MS) analysis and data processing.

ZnONPs from the different assays (migration and *in vitro* digestion assays) were also characterised in terms of concentration (mass and particle number) and size using SP-ICP-MS. An Agilent 7700x ICP-MS equipped with a MicroMist nebulizer and Scott-type spray chamber was used for data acquisition in single particle mode. Default instrumental and data acquisition parameters are listed in Table 1. Samples were diluted with Milli-Q water before SP-ICP-MS measurements with a dilution factor ranged from 1000 to 100000 depending on the background level. Highly diluted samples were required to guarantee that only one particle reaches the detector per dwell time interval. Furthermore, for each sample, data were acquired in triplicate, using a dwell time of 3 ms, an acquisition time of 60s (20000 points) and ^{66}Zn as monitoring isotope. Nebulization efficiency was calculated daily through the analysis of a gold nanoparticle (AuNPs) standard solution prepared by appropriately diluting 30 nm citrate-AuNPs reference material LGC5050 until a concentration of 7.5 ng L^{-1} was reached. Calibration curve of ionic zinc was

prepared daily within the 1-100 ng L⁻¹ range and by employing a zinc standard solution for ICP-MS (Sigma Aldrich).

Raw signal intensity data were processed manually using the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet developed by Abad-Álvaro et al. 2016 [22] from which particle number concentration and particle mass concentration was calculated. Particles were discriminated from the background signal using a 3 σ approach [23]. Particle size diameter and the corresponding size histogram was obtained from the density of ZnO, the mass fraction of Zn/ZnO and by assuming a spherical shape of the nanoparticles. Flow rate and nebulization efficiency values were also considered. This spreadsheet allowed us also to determine the diameter limits of detection (LODd).

3. Results and Discussion.

3.1 Characterization of the ZnONPs

ZnONPs were successfully synthesized through the sol-gel method described in section 2.1 by means of using zinc nitrate as precursor and gelatine as capping agent. The great number of hydroxyl and amine groups in gelatine molecular structure enabled gelatine to coat and stabilize zinc species, therefore inhibiting ZnO-NPs aggregation or crystal growth.

The resulting ZnO nanopowder was fully characterized by applying different techniques. Figures 1a and 1b show the micrographs obtained from TEM and SEM measurements of ZnONPs dispersed in water. The nanoparticles synthesized adopted polygonal shapes with curved ends with a mean diameter of 80 \pm 25 nm, calculated from the *ImageJ* analysis of more than 200 particles found in 10 images (Figure 1, Table 1). Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) analysis evidenced the presence of Zn ((K α (1.0 keV), L α (8.7 keV) and L β (9.6 keV)) in the composition of the nanoparticles. In addition, the electron

diffraction pattern with concentric rings (Figure 1c) confirmed the microcrystalline structure of the synthesized ZnONPs. The FTIR spectrum revealed the presence of an absorption band around 450 cm^{-1} (Figure 1d), associated to a Zn-O bond. Absorption bands associated to organic compounds were not detected indicating that gelatine was completely decomposed during calcination. Additionally, UV-VIS absorption spectrum of ZnONPs shown the characteristic absorption peak close to 364 nm due to $O_{2p} \rightarrow Zn_{3d}$ electronic transition. Shakar *et al.* 2015 also reported the presence of a similar absorption peak of ZnONPs at around 360 nm [24].

The light scattering profiles of the ZnONPs aqueous suspension showed a main scattering peak with a hydrodynamic diameter ranged from 105 to 160 nm. Furthermore, zeta potential value of ZnONPs dispersed in water was around -17 mV. This low zeta potential value provided a weak electrical double layer leading to particle aggregation. This result is in agreement with the images obtained by TEM and SEM and the size distribution measured by DLS.

SP-ICP-MS was subsequently applied to determine both size distribution and NPs concentration (particle per ml and particle mass concentration), as well as the amount of ionic Zn in the nanoparticles suspension. SP-ICP-MS performance parameters were optimized daily following the procedure described in section 2.5. Figure 1.e shows the time scan obtained from a diluted ZnONPs suspension in which a number of spikes above the background level are observed. The frequency of the pulses is proportional to the number concentration of NPs whereas the intensity of each pulse is related to NP size. In this case, events showed a great variability in signal intensity, some of them above 250 counts indicating the formation of large particles ($>150\text{ nm}$) due to particle aggregation as it was previously detected with SEM, TEM and DLS analysis.

Due to the ubiquitous presence of Zn, the application of high dilution factors for ZnONPs suspension was required in order to minimize the background signal. These high dilution factors provided a number of events that were not enough to be statistically significant. To solve this problem and to carry out a proper data evaluation, a minimum of 7 measurements per sample was taken with the aim of obtaining an appropriate number of events (at least 700 events).

The nanoparticle diameter limit of detection (LODd) was calculated to be 26 nm by using the 3σ approach. The value of LODd obtained agreed with those previously reported by Lee *et al.* 2014 and Donovan *et al.* 2016 [25, 26].

Particle diameter was calculated by means of the density of ZnO, the mass fraction of Zn/ZnO and by assuming NPs to be spherical in shape. The diameter size distribution was 90 ± 40 nm with most of nanoparticles sizes ranged between 59 nm and 85 nm as it can be seen in the histogram shown in Figure 1.f. The diameter sizes obtained for the synthesized ZnONPs are in a good agreement with the information on sizes and size distributions given by TEM and DLS measurements.

Particle number concentration was determined from the number of events, the transport efficiency and the sample input flow. For transport efficiency calculations, a suspension of 7.5 ng/L of 30 nm gold NP reference material LGC5050 solution was employed. The solution was prepared daily and the transport efficiency was found to be 7-8%. The ZnONPs concentration was found to be 4.7×10^7 particles/mL or 103 ± 9 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

3.2 Effect of food matrix on physicochemical properties of ZnONPs released from polymeric films

Films loaded with ZnONPs were characterized before and after adding ZnONPs by SEM at different amplification values. The results obtained from PET and LDPE are presented in Figures 2 a, b and 2 c, d, respectively. The images evidence the adherence of ZnONPs on both film surfaces as differences between images before (small images on the right corner) and after the incorporation of ZnONPs into films are clearly observed. The characteristic peaks of zinc in the EDXS spectra ($K\alpha$ (1.0 keV), $L\alpha$ (8.7 keV) and $L\beta$ (9.6 keV)) confirmed the presence of Zn in the nanoparticles detected. SEM images also illustrate a homogeneous distribution of ZnONPs in the film surface without the presence of holes or cracks. The percentage of ZnONPs (as total Zn mass) incorporated into the film was calculated with respect to the amount of Zn initially present in the ZnONPs dispersions employed for preparing ZnONPs loaded films. For this purpose, microwave acid digestion of the films followed by FAAS measurements (section 2.2) was employed. The percentages obtained were $50\pm 12\%$ and $70\pm 10\%$ for PET and LDPE films, respectively. The remaining 50% and 30%, respectively corresponds to the percentage of nanoparticles that was not incorporated in the film and was then removed by using mechanical shaking (Section 2.2).

Results from migration studies performed in juice samples evidenced that around 100% of the zinc contained in PET film migrated to the juice after just only one day of exposure. Figure 3a showed a decrease in size of ZnONPs migrated into the orange juice samples from 80 ± 25 to 11 ± 4 nm after 1 day of contact time. Similar results were obtained for extended contact times (7 and 14 days, Figures 3b and 3c, respectively).

Migration studies by using chicken breast samples provide results slightly different from those obtained in juice. Around a 60% of the Zn contained in the LDPE film migrated into chicken breast at all the times of exposure tested: 1, 14 or 26 days ($50\pm 7\%$, $55\pm 5\%$ and $54\pm 2\%$, respectively). Around a 40% of ZnONPs did not migrate into the food as evidence the results obtained from microwave acid digestion of the film after migration experiments followed by FAAS measurements. The sum of the Zn concentration found in chicken breast and in ZnONPs loaded film after performing migration studies provided recovery values of around 95% of recovery ($93\pm 7\%$, $96\pm 4\%$ and $98\pm 5\%$, for 1, 14 and 26 days of exposure, respectively)

Size and morphological changes once ZnONPs migrated into food was evaluated by TEM and SP-ICP-MS measurements previous isolation of NPs from chicken breast. None of the solutions employed for the extraction steps (aqueous extraction or enzymatic extraction, section 2.3) affected ZnONPs characteristics as it was corroborated by TEM (images not shown). The highest extraction efficiency was obtained when applying aqueous extraction with Tris-HCl (60%). Thus, Tris-HCl was selected as the extracting agent. Figures 3d, e and f shown a decrease in ZnONPs size from 80 ± 25 to 60 ± 23 and 25 ± 12 nm for 1, 14 and 26 days of storage, respectively. Furthermore, aggregates from more than $1\mu\text{m}$ were also observed in samples corresponding to 1 day of exposure. So, results suggest that contact time between nanoparticles and chicken breast matrix notably affects particle size and aggregation degree of ZnONPs.

SP-ICP-MS was also chosen to characterize ZnONPs migrated into food matrices. Pulses above background signal were not detected in the orange juice even after applying high dilution factors (data not shown). Consequently, the characterization of ZnONPs released from film after being in contact with orange juice was not possible as nanoparticles were

below LODd due to the rapid dissolution of ZnONPs. ZnONPs dissolution could be attributed to the low pH value of the orange juice (pH =3.2). The results obtained agreed well with data on nanoparticle size previously obtained by TEM analysis (Figures 3 a, b and c).

In contrast, a significant number of pulses were differentiated from the background signal in chicken samples extracts corresponding to 1 day of storage (Figure 3g). A great variability in signal intensities was obtained. Signal intensities ranged between 450 counts up to more than 15000 counts, indicating the formation of large particles. High background levels were also obtained due to a partial dissolution of ZnONPs when they came in contact with chicken breast. In this case, LODd was found to be 95 nm, almost four times higher than the value previous obtained (26nm) when applying SP-ICP-MS to ZnONPs dispersed in water (discussed in section 3.1).

Under these conditions, the mean size calculated for the ZnONPs was 207 ± 33 nm, mostly within 160-220 nm range as illustrated in the histogram in Figure 3h. Particle number concentration was calculated as 4.73×10^6 particles/mL or 252.8 ± 0.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$ that represents a 26% of the total zinc found in the chicken extracts. Therefore, the percentage of nanoparticles with a size diameter lower than 95 nm, which is the size detection limit, was estimated to be around a 72%.

An increment of the contact time between film and chicken breast had a notably effect on nanoparticles size and aggregation state as no peaks above the signal background were observed (data not shown). This behaviour is likely due to a decrease of particle size below the LODd and a dispersion of the aggregates previously observed in samples obtained after one day of exposure.

Fréchette *et al.* 2019, Donovan *et al.* 2016 and Hadioui *et al.* 2015 also reported the same limitation for the characterization of highly soluble nanoparticles such as ZnONPs and CeO₂ in water by SP-ICP-MS [26-28]. For these complex nanoparticles the authors recommend the use of more than one technique to obtain reliable information on nanoparticles characteristics.

3.4. Evaluation of ZnO-NPs behaviour during an *In Vitro* gastrointestinal digestion assay.

Once ingested, nanoparticles can also modify their size and morphology as they pass through the gastrointestinal tract. Thus, in this work, the gastrointestinal stability of ZnONPs derived from migration studies was evaluated in samples of orange juice and chicken breast by TEM and SP-ICP-MS.

TEM micrographs from orange juice extracts samples after applying the *in vitro* digestion are shown in Figures 4 a, b and c. A noticeable reduction of diameter size from 80 ± 25 (pristine ZnONPs) to 11 ± 4 nm (orange juice) and finally 3.0 ± 0.8 , 2.7 ± 0.5 and 2.6 ± 0.4 nm in oral, gastric and intestinal phase, respectively was obtained. ZnONPs dissolution could be attributed to pH changes occurring during *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion assay.

Percent bioaccessibility was calculated by dividing the Zn concentration in the resulting extracts determined by FAAS (numerator) by the Zn concentration in the food samples before applying the *in vitro* gastrointestinal assay (denominator), and multiplying by 100. The percentage of bioaccessible zinc was 39 ± 1 , 94 ± 3 and $41\pm 3\%$ in oral, gastric and intestine phase respectively (Table 3). These results suggest that ZnONPs exhibit a lower dissolution in digestive fluids with pH close to neutral (salivar and intestine fluids) than in those with a lower pH (gastric fluids pH= 2). Consequently,

the low pH of gastric fluid led to a complete dissolution of ZnONPs as it has been previously reported in the literature for other type of nanoparticles [29-30].

Similar results were observed for chicken breast. There was a decrease in size from 80 ± 25 (ZnONPs pristine dispersion) to 60 ± 23 (chicken breast extract) and finally to 34 ± 8 , 10 ± 1 and 3 ± 1 nm in oral, gastric and gastro-intestinal phase, respectively (Figures 4 d, e, f). TEM micrographs in Figures 4f y d revealed the presence of some aggregates in oral and intestinal phases. In addition, FAAS measurements of oral, gastric and intestine extracts from chicken breast sample provided zinc bioaccessibility values of $0.9\pm 1\%$, $46\pm 11\%$ and $11\pm 1\%$ of the total zinc initially added (Table 3). ZnONPs showed the highest bioaccessible degree in gastric fluid (pH= 2).

The type of food matrix had an important effect on the bioaccessibility of ZnONPs with the lowest percentage in the chicken breast due to interactions between zinc ions released from the dissolution of ZnONPs and proteins from chicken breast [29].

Finally, the extracts obtained after each step of the *in vitro* gastrointestinal process were measured by SP-ICP-MS. In case of juice, pulses above the background signal were not detected even by applying high dilution factors. This results is in agreement with both the high dissolution degree of ZnONPs in gastric extract with a percentage of 93% of bioaccessible Zn (table 2) and the small size of nanoparticles observed by TEM (Figures 4 a, b,-c), which are below of the LODd

However, in case of chicken samples, single events above background signal were found in oral and gastrointestinal phase but, in contrast any signal was observed when gastric extracts were measured (Figure 5 a, b and c). Again, the highest degree of ZnONPs dissolution occurs during the gastric digestion step. This is in agreement with the small

size of the nanoparticles observed in TEM images and with the percentage of Zn found in the gastric step.

High dilution factors were applied to oral and intestinal phase extracts to decrease the background signal with the aim of obtaining information about particle size and particle number and mass concentration. A great number of measurements were also taken in order to achieve a statistically significant number of pulses. Under these conditions, size detection limits of 108 nm and 129 nm for oral phase and gastrointestinal phase, respectively were obtained. Figure 5d shows oral phase size distribution histogram where the diameter sizes of nanoparticles are between 164 nm and 171 nm with a mean size of 174 ± 12 nm. ZnONPs concentration in this phase was found to be of 6.16×10^7 particles/mL or 974.3 ± 0.9 $\mu\text{g/L}$.

Size distribution histogram from intestinal phase (Figure 5 e) evidenced that most of nanoparticles sizes were between 212 nm and 224 nm with a mean diameter size of 223 ± 24 nm. The results may indicate that ZnONPs tend to be aggregated/agglomerated in the transit between the gastric and the intestinal phase. Moreover, the level of ionic Zn decreased in intestinal fluids as it is suggested by the decrease of the background level. All these findings are in good agreement with the low percentage of Zn bioaccessible found in intestinal extracts in comparison with values found in the gastric step. ZnONPs number and mass concentration in this phase was 7.28×10^7 or 2423 ± 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$. The percentage of zinc as ZnONPs in the oral and gastrointestinal phases could not be calculated due to the fact that size detection limits were above 100 nm

Once again, the high values of background produced by ZnONPs dissolution limit the accurate determination of particle size and mass and number concentration of ZnONPs. So, the use of SP-ICP-MS for highly soluble nanoparticles needs to be complemented

with other techniques to corroborate the results obtained. In the current study and due to the combined use of TEM and SP-ICP-MS measurements, it can be concluded that nanoparticles in chicken samples as a consequence of a migration process from food package could reach the intestine wall as small particles (> 10 nm), as aggregates (< 200 nm) and also as ionic zinc leading to an overall percentage of Zn bioaccessible of $11 \pm 1\%$. Concerning to orange juice, only small nanoparticles (< 3 nm) and ionic zinc were detected in the intestinal step.

4. Conclusions

This study clearly evidences the strong effect of food matrices in the fate and behaviour of ZnONPs released from food contact materials. Around 100% of ZnONPs contained in PET films migrated to orange juice after 1 day of exposure whereas a 60% of ZnONPs contained in LDPE films was found in chicken samples. Furthermore, an important decrease in particle size when ZnONPs were in contact with food matrices was noticed being this diminution even more pronounced in juice where ZnONPs as small as 3 nm were detected by TEM measurements.

High background levels of ionic zinc, due to the dissolution of ZnONPs hampered the accurate characterization of ZnONPs in juice samples by SP-ICP-MS. However, SP-ICP-MS allowed us to determine that a 72% of ZnONPs that migrated to chicken breast samples after 1 day of exposure was below 95 nm. The application of SP-ICP-MS has shown limitations when applied to nanoparticles with a great tendency to be dissolved. But even in this unfavourable case, SP-ICP-MS results an useful analytical tool for measuring nanoparticles released from food contact material as well as for estimating the percentage of nanoparticles below or above an established size limit.

Finally, it is important to highlight that the combination of TEM and SP-ICP-MS measurements is required to properly evaluate the effect of food matrix on ZnONPs characteristics and the gastrointestinal fate of ZnONPs once ingested.

Author contributions

All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. ZnONPs characterization by applying different techniques: TEM and SEM images (a y b), electron diffraction pattern (c), FTIR spectrum (d) Time-resolved raw signal data from SP-ICP-MS measurements (e) and size distribution histogram of ZnONPs dispersed in water (f).

Figure 2. SEM images from PET (a) and LDPE (c) films before (upper right side of images) and after being loaded with ZnONPs at low magnification.. SEM images of PET (b) and LDPE (d) films loaded with ZnONPs at high magnification (500 X magnification)

Figure 3. TEM images and XDS spectra from ZnONPs migrated to food after being in contact during 1day (a), 7 days (b) and 14 (c) in case of juice samples and 1 day (d) 14 days (e) and 26 days (f) for chicken breast. Time-resolved SP-ICP-MS raw signal (g) and size distribution histogram (h) of ZnONPs migrated to chicken breast sample after 1 day of exposure.

Figure 4. TEM image and XDS spectra from oral, gastric and intestinal phase of ZnONPs submitted to an *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion procedure after migration (1 day of exposure) to juice (a, b and c) and chicken breast (d, e and f) samples.

Figure 5. Time-resolved SP-ICP-MS raw signal for oral (a), gastric (b) and intestinal extracts (c) after submitting ZnONPs migrated to chicken breast (1 day of exposure) to an *in vitro* gastrointestinal digestion procedure. Size distribution histogram for oral (d) and intestinal (e) phases.

TABLES

Table 1. Operating instrumental conditions

<i>ICP-MS parameters</i>	
RF Power (W)	1250 W
Plasma gas flow rate	15,0 mL min ⁻¹
Ar auxiliary flow rate	1,26 mL min ⁻¹
Carrier gas flow rate	1,1 mL min ⁻¹
Nebulizer	MicroMist
Spray Chamber	Scott
<i>Data acquisition parameters</i>	
Measuring mode	Single particle detection
Dwell time	3 ms
Integration time	60 s
Isotopes monitored	⁶⁶ Zn
<i>FAAS parameters</i>	
Wavelength	213.9 nm
Band pass	0.2 nm
Lamp current	75%
Signal	Continuous
Fuel flow rate (acetylene/air)	2.5/ 4.0 ml min ⁻¹
Flame type	air-acetylene

Table 2. Composition of the solutions employed for performing the *in vitro* gastro intestinal digestion assay.

Artificial Saliva (5 mL)		Gastric Juice (12 mL)		Intestinal juice (17 mL)	
NaCl	9.12 mg	NaCl	51.1 mg	KCl	5.7 mg
CaCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	2.34 mg	KCl	13.8 mg	CaCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	9.4 mg
Na ₂ SO ₄	22.85 mg	KH ₂ PO ₄	4.9 mg	MgCl ₂ *6H ₂ O	4.0 mg
NaHCO ₃	3.2 mg	Mucin	52.5 mg	NaHCO ₃	16.3 mg
KCl	8.1 mg	Pepsin	19.2 mg	Biliar salts	158.5 mg
KH ₂ PO ₄	10.0 mg			Urea	5.5 mg
α-Amilase	5.5 mg			Pancreatin	152.6 mg
Uric acid	0.16 mg			Trypsin	4.1 mg
Urea	1.44 mg				
Mucin	12.62 mg				

Table 3. Percentage of Zn in salivar, gastric and gastro-intestinal simulated extracts^a

	Salivar (% Zn)	Gastric (%Zn)	Gastro-intestinal (%Zn)
Orange Juice	39±1	94±3	41±3
Chicken breast	0.9±0.1	46±11	11±1

Results expressed as (Average ± Stdev, n = 3)

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